

Gravito-Electric Interactions in Atom: A study for stability in static state

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Abstract:

In this paper, we have attempted to study theoretical calculations and contradictions that arises in Gravito-Electric interactions in particles inside atom for stability, with an example of Hydrogen atom.

Introduction:

Proportionality in mass and charge [1], allows us to study theoretical consequences for particles in atom, especially for protons and electrons in their static state, for stability. When electron is dynamic, then it follows as per Bohr's atomic model, Sommerfield's atomic model for describing the motion in dynamics. In static nature, as per two constants G, and K, from Newton's Universal law of gravitation, and Columb's force are discussed, and based on their simple arithmetic calculation, stability during Gravito-Electric interaction are discussed.

As per constant G:(G-explosion), we shall study value of mass of any two electrons, or any two protons, or interaction between proton and electron. Mass, and charge of protons and electrons are well known quantities, and from [1], we can have result as (ratio of mass of particles to charge of particles)

$$\text{G-explosion}(G: =1.347 \times 10^{20})=(1.67262 \times 10^{-27} \times 1.67262 \times 10^{-27}) \text{ kg}/ (1.6 \times 10^{-19} \times 1.6 \times 10^{-19}) \text{ C} = 1.0866 \times 10^{-368} \text{ Kg/C}$$

which results in contradiction, for any two protons.

For two electrons,

$$\text{G-explosion} (1.347 \times 10^{20})= 9.10938356 \times 10^{-31} \times 9.10938356 \times 10^{-31}/ - (1.6 \times 10^{-19} \times 1.6 \times 10^{-19}) = 3.24144147 \times 10^{601}, \text{ which gives another contradiction.}$$

For a proton and an electron (Hydrogen Atom)

G-explosion (1.347×10^{20}) = $5.94244941 \times 10^{303}$, which too results in contradiction.

We have taken mass of proton as 1.67262×10^{-27} , mass of electron as $9.10938356 \times 10^{-31}$, charge of proton as 1.6×10^{-19} , and charge of electron as -1.6×10^{-19} , as per their standard values[2].

As per mathematics, two terms in Right Hand side, and left hand side must be equal for cancellation property, so that, when cancelling out, we can get $1 = 1$, and these contradictions are the places where our theoretical values doesn't matches with experimental values resulting in error.

Conclusion:

We can draw two conclusions from the theoretical contradiction.

1. There isn't any possibility of gravito-electric interactions in static state theoretically, due to contradiction; resulting in mass and charge as two fundamental property of any particles and mass and charge doesn't interact with each other.
2. If mass and charge does interacts with value equalling to that of G-explosion(G:), then new family of particles can be classified based on G:, which provides us with more precise values in calculations due to two fundamental property mass and charge.

Our standard model of particle physics relies in formation of particles by certain atoms, as well as about particles in nature, and in their static state, gravito-electric interactions can be studied, to find any possibility where experimental results may be studied with theoretical results for G:. We studied only Gravitational and Columb's interaction in static model, as mass, and charge as two of fundamental property, and calculated for hydrogen atom, and for any two protons and electrons.

References:

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